

Materials

Oseltamivir phosphate (CAS No. 196618-13-0), L-tyrosine (CAS No. 60-18-4), L-isoleucine (CAS No. 73-32-5), L-serine (CAS No. 56-45-1), L-phenylalanine (CAS No. 63-91-2) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (CAS No. 5470-11-1) were purchased from Sigma/Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Triethylamine (CAS No. 121-44-8) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO, CAS No. 67-68-5) were obtained from BDH (India). MTT ((3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide). Influenza Neuraminidase Inhibitor Susceptibility Assay Kit (ab283398 / abcam/USA). <http://www.abcam.com/ab283398>.